

PHYTOCHEMICAL BASED SOAP: FORMULATION AND EVALUATION STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for herbal and chemical-free cosmetic products has encouraged the development of phytochemical-based formulations with enhanced therapeutic benefits. The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a herbal soap using *Moringa oleifera* and lemongrass essential oil as key active ingredients. *Moringa oleifera* is rich in phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and phenolic compounds, which exhibit antioxidant, antimicrobial, and skin-protective properties. Lemongrass oil is well known for its antibacterial, antifungal, and refreshing fragrance. The soap was formulated using a glycerin base, followed by the incorporation of moringa extract and lemongrass oil in optimized concentrations. The prepared formulation was evaluated for various physicochemical parameters including

pH, moisture content, foam height, foam retention, hardness, and stability. The results demonstrated that the formulated soap had a skin-compatible pH, good foaming ability, and satisfactory physical stability. The presence of phytochemicals contributed to enhanced antimicrobial activity against common skin pathogens. The formulation also exhibited good cleansing efficiency and was found to be non-irritating to the skin. In conclusion, the phytochemical-based herbal soap formulated with moringa and lemongrass oil can be considered a safe, effective, and eco-friendly alternative to conventional soaps, offering both cosmetic and therapeutic benefits.

KEYWORDS: *Moringa oleifera*, Lemongrass oil, Herbal soap, Phytochemicals,

Antimicrobial activity, Antioxidant, Glycerin soap base, Skin care, Formulation, Evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Soap is a cleaner for dirt, dust and bacteria (germs) that stick to the surface of the skin. Soap is a product that is used as a cleaner mixed with water, in general soap is in solid or liquid form.^[1] Herbal soaps are cosmetic cleansing agents prepared using plant-based oils, extracts, and bioactive compounds without the addition of synthetic surfactants or harsh chemicals.^[2]

Herbal soaps that include herbal extracts should have considerable antibacterial, antimicrobial, anti-aging, anti-oxidant, and antiseptic action, promote skin conditioning, have a great foam, have a pleasant aroma, and be soft on the skin. In this study moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) and lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) are used as key herbal ingredients.

Moringa is rich in vitamins, minerals and antioxidants, moringa help in cleansing and nourish the skin, promoting a healthy complexion.^[3] Other benefits of moringa leaves include: giving a feeling of wellness and promotes energy, increases natural body defense, stimulates metabolism, stimulates the cell structure of the body; Rich in vitamin A, provides nourishment to the eyes and brain, balances level of cholesterol, balances level of sugar, rich in antioxidants, beautifies the skin and lowers the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles, improves functioning of kidney and liver, promotes healthy digestion; promotes body's immune system; promotes anti-inflammatory features, heals arthritis pain, heals tumors and ulcers; balances hormone and gland system, detoxify body from poisons, helps relax and promotes good night sleep, and purifies water^[4]. Lemongrass contains essential oils and phenolic compounds that provide antibacterial, antifungal, and refreshing properties.^[5]

Currently available products

- D'Acne soap
- Mannlich Anti Acne soap
- Acnezee soap
- Dermadew Acne soap
- Alite Deep cleansing soap

Limitations of synthetic soap

- Removal of natural oils
- Skin barrier dysfunction

- Irritant contact dermatitis
- pH imbalance
- Allergic reaction.^[6]

Moringa

Fig.1 Moringa leaves.

Synonym: Drumstick

Biological name: *Moringa oleifera*

Biological source: It can consist of dried, long, slender seed-pods of *Moringa oleifera*

Family: Moringaceae.

Chemical constituent - Nitrates, Quercetin, Glucosides.

Geographical source: Moringa is a plant that is native to the sub-Himalayan areas of India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan. It is also grown in the tropics. *Moringa oleifera*, or moringa, is a popular choice for herbal soap due to its numerous skincare benefits. Rich in vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants, moringa helps cleanse and nourish the skin, promoting a healthy complexion. Its anti-inflammatory properties can also soothe skin irritations, making it an excellent ingredient for sensitive skin. Additionally, moringa's natural cleansing properties make it effective in removing impurities and dirt from the skin, leaving it feeling refreshed and rejuvenated.

Uses: Moisturizer, Conditioner, hair growth promoter, cleanser, anti-wrinkle, anti-aging, anti-acne, scar removal, pigmentation, and control for skin infection, sores, as well as sweating, it has also been utilized in cosmeceuticals.^[7]

Lemongrass

Fig. 2 Lemongrass.

Common name: Lemongrass

Biological Source: the volatile oil distilled from *Cymbopogon flexuosus* Stapf and *C. citrates* Stapf.

Family: Graminae

Geographical source: *C. Flexuosus* is indigenous to India and is found in Tinnevely, Travancore and Cochin. *C. citratus* is cultivated in Java, Ceylon, Burma, Madagascar, Mauritius, S. America and W. Indies. In India, it is grown in Punjab, Bombay, Baroda and Mysore.

Chemical Constituents: It contains mainly citral, traces of linalool, citronelal, geraniol, limonene caryophyllene, linalyl and geranyl acetate etc.

Uses: Oil is used in perfumery, soaps, and cosmetics and as a mosquito repellent.

It is used for isolation of citral, which is used for manufacturing ionones. The β -ionone is used for synthesis of Vitamin A.^[8]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ingredients: Moringa oleifera leaves extract, lemongrass oil.

Chemicals: Stearic acid, Sodium hydroxide, Castor oil, Coconut oil, Ethanol, Glycerine, Sugar, Distilled water.^[9]

METHODS

Moringa leaves extract

➤ Fresh Moringa oleifera leaves were collected and cleaned to remove dust and

impurities.

- The leaves were shade dried and then coarsely powdered.
- Moringa leaves extraction is made using the maceration method.
- Moringa leaves powder weighted 60 gm. Were soaked using 300ml of 70% ethanol solvent for 72 hours.
- Stirring occasionally at the same time.
- Then carried out a filtering process then filtered using filter paper and evaporated using water bath.
- Then obtained a thick extract.^[10]

Fig.3 Extraction of Moringa.

Formulation process

Table no. 1: Batches of soap based formulations.

Sr. No.	Ingredients	B1	B2	B3	B4
1.	Coconut oil	25	18.5ml	16.3ml	16.3ml
2.	Stearic acid	-	5gm	7.5gm	7.5gm
3.	Castor oil	-	14ml	5.2ml	5.2ml
4.	NaOH	5gm	3.5ml	3.5gm	3.5gm
5.	Distilled water	50ml	7.5ml	7.5ml	7.5ml
6.	Ethanol	-	3ml	5ml	10ml
7.	Glycerine	2.5ml	7.95ml	5.9ml	5.9ml
8.	Sugar	-	5gm	2.5gm	2.5gm

Note: Batch 3 was optimized formulation, hence it was selected for formulation.

Table no. 2: Batches of Moringa extract concentration formulations.

Sr. No.	Ingredients	B1	B2	B3
1.	Moringa extract	0.4gm	0.2gm	0.3gm
2.	Lemongrass oil	2 drops	2 drops	2 drops
3.	Soap base	50 gm	50 gm	50 gm

Note: Batch 2 was optimized formulation, hence it was selected for formulation.

Procedure of soap base

- First of all, take coconut oil, castor oil in a 100 ml beaker.
- Put the beaker in a water bath and stir boil it until a strong consistency form at a temperature between 40°C to 45°C.
- Then take a NaOH dissolve in distilled water in another beaker and mixed properly.
- After preparing, this solution was added slowly in oil mixture with constant stirring.
- Add glycerine, ethanol.
- Then this mixture was boil at 40°C to 45°C until base consistency and pour the mixture into soap moulds.
- Allow to set.

Procedure

- Take 50 gm of soap base in a beaker and put on water bath at 45°C.
- Then add the moringa leaves extract and lemongrass oil with continuous stirring in to soap base.
- Boil the mixture on the water bath 45°C and soap mixture is prepared.
- Prepared soap mixture is filled in soap mould.
- Mould is put in the refrigerator for 15 minutes.
- After solidification cut the soap mould using cutter or blade.
- Then obtained herbal soap.^[11]

Evaluation Parameters

- **Colour:** When visualizing the herbal soap, a white background was used so that the colour could be determined and so that the clarity of formulations is seen.
- **Odour/Aroma:** An evaluation of the odour of formulations we used two different methods. The first method included heating the sample on a hot plate.
- **Shape:** Evaluation of organoleptic properties, such as shape and clarity, was carried out by sensory examination.^[12]
- **pH:** 5 to 6 g of the soap was weighted accurately in a 100ml beaker 40ml water was added and dispersed the soap in it. The pH of the solution is determined by using pH meter.^[13]

Fig. 4 pH Meter.

Determination of TFM (Total Fatty Matter): By reacting soap with acid in the presence of hot water and measuring the resulting fatty acid, TFM was determined. After dissolving 10g of the designed soap in 150ml of distilled water, the mixture was heated. 20 ml of 15% H₂SO₄ were added to this and heated until a clear solution was achieved. The resulting solution's surface fatty acid was solidified by heating it once again and adding 7g of beeswax. It was then permitted to cake. After removing the cake, it was blotted dry and weighed using formula.

$$\%TFM = \frac{\text{weight of a cake} - \text{weight of the wax in gm}}{\text{weight of the soap in gm}} \times 100^{[14]}$$

Fig. 5 Total Fatty Matter.

- **Moisture content:** About 10 gram of the material were heated in a hot air oven at 100 to 105 degrees Celsius for an hour. After that deducted the true weight of the tarred china dish from the total weight of the sample and dish. The weight of the material was recorded, and the method for calculating the percentage of the moisture content that can be found in it is shown below formula.

Moisture Content = Initial wt. - Final wt. / Initial wt. × 100.

Fig. 6: Moisture content.

Foam Forming Ability: The Cylinder Shake Method was utilized to determine the Foaming ability. First, in a 100 ml measuring cylinder, we put 50 ml of a 1% sample solution and shaken vigorously 10 times. After shaking for 1 minute, we measured the height of the foam that had formed and recorded the total volume of foam.

Fig.7 Foam Forming Ability.

➤ **Foam Stability:** The Cylinder Shake Method was utilized to determine the Foaming ability. First, in a 100ml measuring cylinder, we put 50 ml of a 1% sample solution. The cylindrical container was covered up with the use of the hand and shaken vigorously 10 times. The volume of the foam after ten minutes was calculated.

Fig. 8 Foam Stability.

- **Skin Irritation test:** For the determination of irritancy test, Use the soap sample on clean skin to observe. For signs of irritation, such as redness, burning, or itching and 24 hours, the situation was monitored.^[15]

Fig.9 Skin Irritation Test.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation Test Result

Parameters	Observational Value	Standard Value
pH	8.20	7-10
Total Fatty Matter	60%	50-70%
Moisture content	24.45%	15-25%
Foam forming ability	9cm	10cm
Foam stability	5cm	5cm
Skin irritation test	No	No

CONCLUSION

The present investigation focused on the formulation and evaluation of a phytochemical-based herbal soap incorporating moringa extract and lemongrass essential oil. The study demonstrated that the integration of plant-derived bioactive constituents into a soap base can significantly enhance its functional and therapeutic properties. The formulated herbal soap exhibited satisfactory physicochemical parameters, including suitable pH, good foaming capacity, optimal hardness, and stability. The presence of moringa extract contributed notable antioxidant and skin-conditioning effects, while lemongrass oil imparted antimicrobial activity along with a characteristic refreshing fragrance. The evaluation results confirmed that the formulation is safe, effective, and non-irritant for topical application. The findings support the potential of phytochemical-based herbal soaps as a promising alternative to conventional synthetic formulations, aligning with the growing demand for natural, eco-friendly, and skin-compatible products. However, further studies involving long-term stability assessment, microbial challenge tests, and clinical evaluation are recommended to validate its efficacy and scalability for commercial application.

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